

The Covid-19 Pandemic in Saudi Arabia: Reinforcing National Identity and the Challenges to Religious Facets

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Abstract

The outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic was accompanied by a fierce race in scientific and academic publications from various disciplines. However, the social and humanities fields were scant in their output. The value of protecting the country (Saudi Arabia) through the campaign, #Weareallresponsible, which necessitated staying home for the safety of others and the discomfort experienced by those who witnessed the social distancing between the ranks of the worshippers in mosques while shushing: “set the rows in order, stand shoulder to shoulder, close the gaps”, calls for research within the context of identity upon crises to revisit several social and religious taboos. Moreover, the “safe social distancing,” which was imposed at the start of the pandemic (March 2020) for a total of five months (August 2020),¹ enables researchers to examine the phenomenon *after the storm subsided*—so to speak—and to look through the perspective of an observer rather than a participant. This work examined two questions: 1) How did the Covid-19 pandemic reinforce Saudi national identity? (2) At the same time, how did it challenge the religious identity facets? This paper tried to answer these questions by employing a qualitative approach through analysing a number of tweets and their interactions (between March and July 2020) on two Twitter accounts: a) the Saudi Ministry of Health @SaudiMOH; and b) the Saudi Ministry of Islamic Affairs @Saudi_Moia. The results can be summarised as follows: The Saudi Ministries of Health and Islamic Affairs employed the national and religious identity facets by reinforcing the first and facing the challenges of the latter through a discourse that focused on social responsibility, heroism and duty and the concept of national health security, all to raise the level of commitment to precautionary measures during the pandemic of Covid-19. The encounters with religious identity appeared in avoiding shaking hands, disapproving of the social distance between worshippers and wearing a face mask.

Keywords: COVID 19, Pandemic, Mask, Saudi Arabia, National Identity

¹ Social distance was applied again with the outbreak of the second wave of the Corona virus: Omicron.

Contribution/Originality: This work aimed to record part of the social memory of Saudi society amidst the Covid-19 pandemic crisis and to enrich the literature landscape on identity during a crisis within the Islamic, Arabic, Gulf and Saudi contexts.

Glossary of Terms

Identity

In our eastern Arab society, it is the nation, the society and the homeland in its collective form. The individual can acquire his/her identity through his affiliation with this group, as he or she do not have an individual and personal identity without a sense of belonging to the collective identity (Al-Sultani & Al-Shammari, 2019).

National Identity

It is the final outcome of the people's culture and civilisation's inheritance and a set of commonalities that distinguish people from other peoples in the world (Ibid, 2019). The Saudi national identity consists of five components: religion, language, origin, geography and culture (Al-Subaie, M et al., 2019).

Religious Identity

In Saudi Arabia, the religious identity is the Islamic identity, following the Islamic religion, adhering to its pillars and performing its duties. The literature indicates that the two sides of national and religious identity in Saudi Arabia are inseparable. To be a Saudi is to be a Muslim (Watson, 1987).

Introduction

In December 2019, the news of a new epidemic outbreak in the city of Wuhan, the People's Republic of China, began to spread around the world. In its early stages, it was not a threat to those outside those geographical borders, but the transmission of the nature of this epidemic, its symptoms, methods of infection and prevention and the availability (or not) of treatment were present on television screens, social media platforms—especially Twitter—and certainly in the medical community and scientific journals. On 2 March 2020, the Saudi

Ministry of Health recorded the first case of Covid-19. Events accelerated, and attendance of schools, universities and workplaces was banned between 8–15 March 2020. The total ban was loosened from time to time until a cautious return to (almost) normal life on 21 June 2020.

This paper argues its contribution in light of the scarcity in the research landscape of studies that addressed the relationship between identity and the Covid-19 pandemic, specifically within the Islamic, Arab, Gulf and Saudi contexts. Moreover, methodically, this work gains its value through the qualitative data collection and analysis methods, under the prevalence of quantitative descriptive methods, such as surveys, questionnaires or scales, in the existing Arabic academic literature within the social sciences and humanities fields. On the other hand, the choice of Twitter as a source of data can be explained by a number of justifications. 1) It is important to capture the discussions and conversations that occur on social media platforms (SMPs) for a better understanding of human behaviour during epidemics and change possible strategies to combat the epidemic (Hamwi, 2020) The Twitter platform is a rich medium that can be leveraged to understand public sentiment in real time and target public health messages based on user interests and passion (Medford et al., 2020) The platform's activities responded and reacted to events related to the Covid-19 pandemic (Chen et al., 2020).

Finally, this work recorded part of the social memory of Saudi society during the crisis of the Covid-19 pandemic. This paper raised a key question: *How did the Covid-19 pandemic reinforce the Saudi national identity and, at the same time, how did it challenge the religious identity facets?* It is organised as follows: starting with a theoretical review, followed by the methodology and analysis, and in closing, the conclusion and discussion.

Figure. 1 Two tweets. The first depicts part of the religious identity challenge: “One of Corona’s paradoxes: the Imam used to say, “straighten your rows.” Will he be saying tomorrow, “separate your rows”? In the blink of an eye and its attention, God changes from case to case. May God have mercy on us and forgive us.

The second tweet shows the application of social distancing in the Great Mosque of Mecca: “The application of #distancing among worshippers in the Holy Mosque in Macca today within ālṭrāwyḥ prayer #mecca #holy_mosque”

Figure.2 A tweet depicts the use of the fatwa following the application of the spacing between the rows of worshippers in the Grand Mosque in Makkah: “Debate and questioning have abounded these days due to the #coronavirus over the issue of distancing in prayers in

mosques. What impact does this have on prayer health? Sheikh Fahad al-Amari's answers by in a brief research: The religious injunction of #Prayer with distancing rows."

Literature Review

Covid-19 Pandemic and Symbolism of Heroism in Containing the Pandemic

As mentioned, academic work that tackled the pandemic from a social perspective in general is limited; moreover, narrowing such a focus to those within Saudi Arabia decreases the volume from limited to scarce. Al-Dharmi et al. (2020) discussed the Saudi public's perceptions of and commitment to social distancing during the Covid-19 pandemic, aiming to assess the awareness and commitment of the Saudi people to social distancing measures through an electronic questionnaire tool. One of their most prominent findings was that the Saudi Ministry of Health was the main source of information about the pandemic, that the general implementation of social distancing was satisfactory and that the plans organised by the Saudi Ministry of Health were effective in raising awareness and improving the practice of social distancing among the Saudi public. Al-Juhaiman (2020) studied the societal repercussions of the Covid-19 crisis on families in Riyadh, arguing that the societal repercussions contributed to the availability of electronic platforms that provided education and improved the skills of children and their families and that non-profit organisations presented value competitions targeting family members through learning and entertainment. Pogrebna and Kharlamov (2020) examined the impact of cultural differences—handwashing patterns—on the extent of the spread of Covid-19 and the preference for handwashing culture in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia among 63 countries. This was related to the slow spread of Covid-19 in the Kingdom compared to other countries, which could be argued to be due to the impact of the social and cultural context on limiting the spread of epidemics, given the status of purity (*Tahara*) in Islam and the constitution of culture in Saudi Arabia.

Analysis of Covid-19 Pandemic on Twitter

Data Collection and Analysis Using Data Mining and Artificial Intelligence

In view of the scarcity of qualitative analytical studies that dealt with the digital content of the Covid-19 pandemic via social media platforms, a large number of quantitative

studies analysed pandemic-related tweets through data mining and artificial intelligence via platforms, such as Twitter API, Python and machine learning models that recognise and categorise feelings and emotions. Their findings can be summarised as follows:

- Considering the public perception of Covid-19 and social distancing and analysing the hashtags, #stayathome and #socialdistancing, the general conclusion was that Twitter users supported social distancing in the early stages of its implementation (Ding et al., 2020).
- Determining the aspects of social distancing during the Covid-19 pandemic, it was found that the dominance of tweets related to aspects of “implementation” of social distancing and “negative emotions” towards it, which were related to the topics of “social disorder” and “adaptation” (Kwon et al., 2020).
- Leveraging high-volume Twitter data to understand the general sentiments of the Covid-19 outbreak. In analysing sentiment to determine emotional valence and prevalent emotions, nearly half of the tweets (49.5%) expressed fear and about 30% expressed surprise (Medford et al., 2020).

These studies correspond with a paucity of work that has analysed Arab tweets using the same techniques in analysis and data collection about the pandemic. For example, Al-Sudais and Rayson (2020) discussed how governments of the Arab world and public health institutions could benefit from social media? The main topics discussed were Covid-19 statistics, praying for God, Covid-19 websites, advice and education for prevention and advertising. Mustafa et al. (2020) attempted to measure the general reaction to the pandemic, which resulted in six main themes: feelings and emotions, information, public discussion, politics, food and sarcasm or humour. Finally, Hamwi et al. (2020) analysed the main topics discussed among Arab users, which were preventive measures in various Arab countries, supplications, news and reports, and topics related to preventing the spread of the disease, such as curfews and quarantine.

Data Collection and Analysis Using Qualitative Methodology

Al-Anazi's (2020) study on public relations through social media platforms and health crisis management is among the few Arabic works that discuss the management of the Covid-19 crisis through the Iraqi Ministry of Health's (IMH) Facebook page. Al-Anazi utilised observation and content analysis methodology to examine the role of IMH's public relations

in managing the Covid-19 health crisis, diversifying the content of the IMH media account and using it extensively during the pandemic, including providing the public with news and ensuring that they did not panic. Ajayi et al. (2020) also analysed Facebook content to evaluate the accuracy and reliability of information during pandemics using a mixed methods (qualitative and quantitative) approach. It concluded that interaction with interest-bearing posts was higher compared to its misleading and non-pandemic-related counterparts.

Reinforcing National Identity and the Media, Challenges of Religious Identity and the Covid-19 Pandemic

One of the few works that discussed reinforcing national identity was by Al-Aboud (2020), who attempted to identify the Saudi public's attitudes towards the role of Saudi television channels in preserving national identity through a questionnaire. One of the most prominent results of Al-Aboud's study was that "the Saudi audience considers television as a major source of building and strengthening national identity, and that preserving national identity is different from building it." The works by Rabhi (2013), Khanish (2019) and Al-Muhaizeh et al. (2017) used research methodologies that were most relevant to the current paper, qualitative analysis depicting the symbols of national identity, such as the homeland. Rabhi (2013), Khanish (2019) employed a content analysis method to uncover the reinforcing of national identity in the school curriculum. On the other hand, Al-Muhaizeh et al. (2017) analysed the role of digital media in reinforcing Bahraini national identity. They concluded that the new media tended to promote positive values within the context of Bahraini national identity.

Regarding religious identity and Covid-19, Silva (2020) and Safdar and Yasmin (2020) addressed the challenges of the religious identity of Muslims in Sri Lanka and women in Pakistan, respectively. In Sri Lanka, the results found racism being practised against Muslims by accusing them of causing the spread of the epidemic due to the failure to apply distance between prayer lines and their refusal to cremate the bodies of their dead. The Pakistani woman faced a challenge to her gender identity and work during the ban period, which limited her to being housewives and imposed the stereotypical role of women in the home in light of their inability to go out to work.

Symbolism of Heroism in the Containment of the Pandemic

Atlani-Duault et al. (2020) and Einboden (2020) considered earlier works that traced the rise of the symbolism of online heroism during epidemics, using qualitative analysis to identify the challenges facing authorities in dealing with pandemic crises. Atlani-Duault et al. concluded that there was a tendency by public authorities during crises to focus their attention on reducing panic and filtering the information they provided to the public. Einboden discussed and analysed the symbolism of the exceptional nurse and the dilemma of the use of heroic language in the health sector during the Covid-19 pandemic. The author concluded that the discourse of heroism was filled with wartime terminology and military metaphors and that the media and medical leadership were working to “produce and perpetuate healthcare workers as heroes in a war between Covid-19 and humanity”.

Methodology

This work employed a qualitative approach to collect, analyse data and present findings, as “the qualitative nature of the research allows for a comprehensive understanding of the subject of the study. Because qualitative research is interpretive, explanatory, inductive, multi-methodological, and in-depth, as it is flexible and sensitive to the particularities of the respondents and their social context” (Delio, 2015). The data were collected manually via Twitter by collecting tweets on the Saudi Ministry of Health account.

Interaction with a number of tweets from the account of the Ministry of Islamic Affairs between 21 March 2020 and 31 July 2020, with a total of 119 tweets (87 tweets for the Saudi Ministry of Health and 18 tweets for the Ministry of Islamic Affairs). The focus was on tweets that used the hashtag #We_are_all_responsible on the account of the Saudi Health Twitter account, and the tweets regarding the application of precautionary measures (social distancing) on the Ministry of Islamic Affairs’ Twitter account from March–July 2020. Tweets were chosen according to the following considerations:

1. The period between the beginning of the ban and the pandemic in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and the return to almost normal life: #we_return_with_caution.
2. Tweets were obtained through the two accounts if they contained content relevant to this paper.

Thematic analysis was used to analyse the tweets, which can be defined as: “A type of qualitative analysis that is used to analyse ratings and present themes (patterns) that relate to data. It clarifies the data in great detail and deals with various topics through interpretations” and is characterised by providing “flexibility to start data analysis at any time during the project, as there is no correlation between the data collected and the results of the process itself”. This applies to the type of data covered in this research, as a period of time elapsed between tweets and when the data were collected and analysed.

Thematic analysis was applied as follows:

- 1 - The number of tweets was calculated and put into a table.
- 2 - The data were read more than once to identify and reach familiarity with the data.
- 3 - General description of the data: their numbers, their classifications: text, image, GIF, video clips and links, in addition to using Word Cloud for text tweets.
- 4 - The content of the Saudi Ministry of Health’s (text) tweets was coded and analysed to answer the research question: How did the Covid-19 pandemic enhance Saudi national identity?
- 5 - The content of the tweets by the Ministry of Islamic Affairs was coded and analysed to answer the research question: How did the novel Covid-19 pandemic pose a challenge to religious identity?

This was followed by writing the analysis section using the following steps:

- 1 – Building the most prominent themes that emerged through data analysis, with descriptions and examples of each theme.
- 2 – Linking the results to the literature review and writing the discussion section.

Finally, because of time constraints, the researcher was not able to share data coding and themes with other researchers, which are among the components of validity and reliability in qualitative research. However, other elements of those components were achieved through data collection and analysis, including the following (Delio, 2015):

- **Transparency:** As mentioned, the data were reviewed more than once, and all the steps of data collection and analysis were clearly and transparently presented in the methodology section.

– **The threat of bias:** I (the researcher) have no connection (officially or unofficially) to the work of the two ministries and have no reason to frame the data in a biased way. In addition, through the clarification, I indicated my prior expectations, which were contradicted by analysing the data, specifically in the interactions with tweets by the Ministry of Islamic Affairs on the issue of religious identity challenges.

– **Prolonged participation in the field; Immersion or Crystallisation:** I have extensive experience in employing the qualitative method in scientific research throughout my academic publishing career. In addition, I have more than 20 years of experience in the use of social media.

Data Analysis

Data Description

In this section, I provide a general description of the tweets by the Saudi Ministry of Health and the Ministry of Islamic Affairs that were collected during the period between 21 March 2020 and 31 July 2020 through:

A. Media used: GIF, images, videos, infographics and others

B. The hashtags used, which show the sequence of the pandemic's stages from the beginning (#We_are_all_responsible) to its return (#We_return_with_caution).

A- Media Used in Tweets

Description of the Tweets by the Saudi Ministry of Health

Frequency	Media Used
4	GIF
6	Image
43	Video
7	Photo
1	Link
19	Infographic
1	Hashtag Ad
6	Combination ¹
87	Total

Table 1. Classification of media used in tweets on the Saudi Ministry of Health's account²

Table (1) above depicts that videos and the infographics obtained the majority in the methods used to deliver, display and present content through the account of the Saudi Ministry of Health during the period from 21 March 2020 to 31 July 31 2020. This marks the beginning of the Covid-19 pandemic until the return to semi-normal life at the end of Shawwal 1441 AH³. It is important to clarify that the analysis of the data in this paper was limited to the analysis of text tweets only, meaning that the analysis of the media content below was outside the focus of this work. It was also noted that the duration of each video clip did not exceed one minute, which gives the message two advantages: shortness and movement. In

¹ The use of more than one medium in a single tweet.

² **Photo** means photographs, whether ordinary, personal or digital, which were taken, for example, of people.

Image means virtual images such as Photoshop designs.

³ End of first wave of Covid-19

addition, two styles, storytelling and preaching (Table 5), were used in most of the videos. The reasons for the dominance of these two methods were the rate of interaction (the number of views etc.). Finally, the infographic style can be distinguished by its clarity and definition.

Description of Tweets in the Ministry of Islamic Affairs Account

Despite the limited number of tweets distributed by the Ministry of Islamic Affairs (Table 2) compared to the tweets by the Saudi Ministry of Health (Table 1), they used a higher number of video clips compared to other media (photos, infographics, etc.), although the difference between them is not provided numerically. Moreover, compared to the use of the two methods of storytelling and preaching in the tweets by the Saudi Ministry of Health, the Ministry of Islamic Affairs used the following methods: explanation—how to apply the precautionary measures and semi-documentary—presenting interviews with worshippers to convey their impressions of the application of precautionary measures in mosques.

What is striking here is the absence of any preaching video clip; a sheikh doing a presentation about the application of precautionary measures, compared to the clips contained in the account of the Saudi Ministry of Health. This raises a number of questions, including: Is it because the account belongs to the Ministry of Islamic Affairs, so that there is no need to address the relationship between religious sentiments and precautionary measures? Or is this due to coordination between the two ministries with regard to media content? These and other questions are beyond this work's focus and may be addressed in future work.

Table 2. Classification of media used in tweets on the account of the Ministry of Islamic Affairs

Frequency	Media Used
0	GIF
1	Image
5	Video
4	Photo(s)
0	Link
3	Infographic

0	Hashtag Ad
5	Combination
18	Total

B - Tags Used in Tweets

Tags used on the Saudi Ministry of Health Twitter Account

The hashtag #We_are_all_responsible was the main hashtag, followed by #Corona_Prevention, which was used in almost half of the tweets. The community heroes tag was used in the previously mentioned storytelling content¹ by portraying several “model citizens”; people whose behaviour is exemplary, of different ages and with different jobs who care for those infected with Covid-19. As for the #stay_at_home, it was used during periods of total and partial bans to emphasise the importance of staying at home and the impact of this on limiting the spread of the epidemic. As for the two hashtags, #Corona and #COVID19, they were used occasionally (11 times) in different tweets. The three hashtags, #dontsaydone, accepting house invitations or visits; #you_are_excused, avoiding gatherings and refusing to shake hands and #celebrateahealthyeid, during the period of Eid al-Fitr, when the total ban was applied for a period of 3 days (1–4 Shawwal), were used within the social and family frameworks that warn against placing the priority of fulfilling social and family obligations above the priority of reducing the spread of the epidemic for which the ban was established. Finally, the hashtag #return_with_cautiousness came to identify the beginning of the stage of returning to almost normal life that was referred to previously.

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Table 3. Tags used on the Saudi Ministry of Health's Twitter account

التكرار	الوسوم المستخدمة	التكرار	الوسوم المستخدمة
4	#COVID19	46	#الوقاية من كورونا #CovidPrevention
1	#لا تقول تم #Dontsaydone	89	#كلنا مسؤول #Weareallreasonable
1	#عاذرينكم #Youareexcused	6	#أبطال المجتمع #Communityheroes
1	#عيد بصحة #Celebratehealthyeid	3	#خلك بالبيت #Stayathome
3	#نعود بحذر #Returningwithcautiousness	7	#كورونا #Corona
	72 ¹		Total

Tags used on the Ministry of Islamic Affairs Twitter Account

Table 4. The hashtags used on the Ministry of Islamic Affairs Twitter account

التكرار	الوسوم المستخدمة
2	#كورونا #Corona
2	#نعود بحذر

¹ ليستثنى منها تكرار 89 لوسم كلنا مسؤول لأنه تكرر في جميع التغريدات

	#Returningwithcautious
3	#بسلام_آمنين #safeinpeace
2	#حج_1441 #Haj1441
1	#عيد_الأضحى #AladhaEid #مشعر_مزدلفة #theMonumentofMuzdalifah #المشعر_الحرام #SacredMonument
10	Total

The stages and content of the hashtags used by the account of the Ministry of Islamic Affairs were classified into three stages: prior to the opening of mosques at the end of May 2020, to explain the precautionary measures and preparing mosques prior to their opening. This was followed by the stage of cautiously returning at the end of July 2020, containing pictures of worshippers and the application of social distancing and interviews with worshippers on their impressions of the application of precautionary measures. Finally, the Hajj and Eid al-Adha stages followed the return stage by about two months and contained pictures and videos of pilgrims to the Holy House of God and the holy sites.

Data Analysis

As mentioned in the methodology section, the two stages of analysis were as follows: encoding the tweets on the Saudi Ministry of Health account and then collecting them under similar grouping categories to display them as themes, and then applying the same tool to the tweets on the account of the Ministry of Islamic Affairs (only) with the intention of focusing

on the challenge of religious identity in the application of social distancing between the ranks of worshippers in prayer and other precautionary measures.

Coding the Tweets of the Saudi Ministry of Health

With a total of 87 tweets, 54 symbols were extracted, categorised according to the number of their repetitions within 3 groups, with 18 symbols for each group: the highest frequency (19,17,13,8), the average frequency (7,6,5,4) and the lowest frequency (3, 2,1) (Table 5). The symbols were then categorised into 12 categories (Table 6) that formed a partial analysis with a focus on two categories: religious identity and national identity, mainly according to the topic of this paper.

Table 5. Encoding tweets by the Saudi Ministry of Health

1	الأجر Reward (āl'gr)	3	الوطن Homeland	5	السنة النبوية Prophetic Sunnah	19	الهوية الدينية Religious identity
1	البر Philanthropy	3	الوعي Awareness (noun)	5	القيم المجتمعية Social values	17	المسؤولية المجتمعية Social responsibility
2	البلاء Affliction	2	الاحتساب Imputation	5	الهوية الوطنية National identity	13	الوقاية Precaution
1	التفاني Dedication	2	الأمن الصحي الوطني National health security	5	الوباء The epidemic	8	المسؤولية الأسرية Familial responsibility
1	السؤال Questioning	2	التباعد Distancing	4	الأخذ بالأسباب Adopting means to reach an end	7	البقاء في المنزل Staying home
1	الشرف Honour	2	التعاون Cooperation	4	التسليم Submission (to destiny)	7	المسؤولية الفردية Personal responsibility
1	العلاقة الزوجية Marital relationship	2	التفاؤل Optimism	4	الحذر من التجمعات Caution of gatherings	7	المواطنة Citizenship
1	المشاركة	2	الدعاء	4	الحس الجمعي	6	الالتزام

	Participation		āld'ā'		Collective sense		Commitment
1	الواجب Duty	2	الرعاية Welfare	4	الرضا Fulfilment	6	الترهيب Intimidation
1	ذوي الاحتياجات الخاصة Disabled	2	العزل Isolation	4	العادات والتقاليد Values and traditions	6	التوعية Awareness (verb)
1	طاعة الله Obedience to Allah	2	القدوة Role model	3	الأمن Safety	6	القرآن Quran
		2	تحدي الهوية الدينية The challenge of religious identity	3	التوكل āltwkl Reliance	6	القصة The story
		2	دور الوعي The role of awareness	3	الحماية Protection	6	مهارات التواصل اللغوي Verbal communication skills
		2	فائدة الوعي The benefit of awareness	3	الذنب Sin	5	الاستجابة Responsiveness
		1	الاستفهام Interrogation	3	الصبر Patience	5	البطولة Heroism
		2	الاطمئنان Reassurance	3	المسافة Distance	5	البيت The house

Table .5 Classifying the encoding of tweets by the Saudi Ministry of Health into categories

<p>The benefit of awareness</p> <p>Awareness</p> <p>The role of awareness</p> <p>Spreading awareness</p>	<p>Cautious from gatherings</p> <p>Precaution</p> <p>Distant</p> <p>Intimidation</p> <p>Staying home</p> <p>Distancing</p> <p>Isolation</p>	<p>National identity</p> <p><u>Sacred texts</u></p> <p>Quran</p> <p>Prophetic Sunnah</p> <p><u>Religious values</u></p> <p>Reward (āḷġr)</p> <p>Fulfilment</p> <p>Patience</p> <p>Obedience to Allah</p> <p>Affliction</p> <p>Imputation</p> <p>Take account of mitigating factors</p> <p>Affliction</p> <p>āld‘ā’</p> <p>Submission (to destiny)</p> <p>The challenge of religious identity</p>
<p><u>Human values</u></p> <p>Philanthropy</p> <p>Dedication</p> <p>Honour</p> <p>Commitment</p>	<p>Traditions and values</p> <p>Familial responsibility</p> <p>Marital relationship</p> <p>Welfare</p> <p>House</p>	<p>Social responsibility</p> <p>Collective sense</p>

cooperation	Social values	
Health national security Safety National identity Homeland Citizenship	Verbal communication skills (linguistics) Disabled (sign language)	<u>Styles of discourse</u> Story Sin Preaching Protection Questioning Interrogation
Reassurance Optimism	Duty Heroism Role model	Individual responsibility Responsiveness Participation

Figure. 3 A Word cloud of the Saudi Ministry of Health Twitter account tweets

Reinforcing National Identity

Figure 1

Social Responsibility, Heroism, Duty, Security and Gratitude

A number of tweets by the Saudi Ministry of Health used national identity as motivation in different facets: social responsibility, heroism, duty, security and gratitude, all with the aim of urging adherence to precautionary measures and other means to reduce the epidemic. For example, in (Figure 4), in the first tweet⁷, the infographic and picture were used together: *Our heroes are the security men in the field. You are the watchful eyes of the homeland, and in the interest of your health, we offer you these important tips that will help you, God willing, in preventing infection.* The picture is of a soldier affiliated with Public Security wearing a mask and guiding citizens in their vehicles on the road. In another tweet⁸, *Staying at home protects the homeland*, came with a picture of one of the main roads in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, using the two logos of the Ministry of Health and using red colour as the background for the same phrase on the image, in addition to the sentence, *Do not move unless necessary.* In the third tweet, *From our operating rooms to your operating rooms, thank you*, the military and medical operations appear as two defence fronts against the epidemic by placing the phrase, *You are the heroes of the field*, on the picture. Here, the concept of championship comes to include both professions: military and medicine (Figure 4).

⁷ The first tweet from the left

⁸ The tweet in the middle in (Figure 4)

National Health Security

Figure 2

The main objective of this paper was to analyse the reinforcing of national identity in the tweets by the Saudi Ministry of Health during the Covid-19 pandemic, while analysing the challenges of religious identity by the Ministry of Islamic Affairs in interacting with the tweets in its account in applying social distancing in holy places. However, the two facets of the Saudi national and religious identity intersected through the tweets by the Saudi Ministry of Health, meaning that the religious discourse included the reinforcing of the national identity, all with the aim of contributing to urging Saudi citizens to adhere to precautionary measures.

We found this in two tweets (Figure 5) in which members of the Council of Senior Scholars appeared: Sheikh Saad bin Nasser Al-Shathri and Sheikh Abdullah Al-Mutlaq, who presented two clips urging citizens to adhere to precautionary measures. The first⁹ introduced the

⁹ From the right.

term national health security: *The safety of society, an honour to which soldiers dedicate their time and health in order to preserve national health security*, through stimuli of a sense of community, social responsibility, and the value of honour; all to clarify the efforts made by the soldiers of the country. This brings us back to the second paragraph of the previous point and the tweet, *From our operating rooms to your operating rooms, thank you*, which shows the extension of doctors alongside the military concept of soldiers.

The second tweet¹⁰ connected religious values, trust and reason, in addition to individual and national responsibility: preserving the health of the homeland (Figure 5: *And in God, trust if you are believers. Relying on God in delegating matters to Him and not leaving the causes comes with the individual sensing the importance of following the matter to preserve the health of the body and the homeland. Here, the Ministry of Health employed religious discourse through members of the Council of Senior Scholars, whose words are heard by all Muslims in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia; the citizens and residents of Saudi Arabia. In addition to the divine discourse (the Qur'anic verse) to raise Muslims' response to abide by the precautionary measures of staying at home, were linked to the national identity: preserving the homeland is part of the religious duty of the Muslim individual.*

In addition, there is an aspect of the religious identity challenge, which is the value of reliance, which may lead to underestimating the obligation to stay at home and other precautionary measures. This is where the religious discourse comes in and is combined with accepting reason and national duty, in the face of the potential neglect of *TawaaKul* (dependency) instead of *Tawakkul* (trust in Allah). The third tweet: *The virtue of peace these days is achieved through the tongue, because shaking hands is a cause for the spread of the epidemic, and avoiding it is a matter that must be followed in compliance with the preventive instructions.* Warning against shaking hands, which carries a high religious value: [There are no two Muslims who meet and shake hands, but that they are forgiven before they part] – Prophet Mohammed. The epidemic turned the handshake into a carrier of the epidemic, and here, a religious duty turned into a taboo through religious discourse as well. The challenge of religious

¹⁰ In the middle.

the ministry responded to in tweets. On the other hand, others posted their comments about not applying the same procedures:

Your responsibility for these restriction has ended. Talking is easy, but implementation is difficult. The restrictions were applied firmly so as not to take us back to the way we were, because today I witnessed the astonishment of people as they prayed as before, shoulder-to-shoulder without sleeve, carpets, and no distancing for fear that the mosques will be closed again if the situation continues as it does.

In addition, a facet of the national identity appeared in a number of proud tweets by neighbourhood residents showing their commitment to precautionary measures in the mosque:

As for the congregation of our mosque, the truth and the truth is, I say: They adhered to all the precautionary measures and with utmost precision, and we did not see anything noticeable worth mentioning! They are a very proud, educated and obedient society with a high degree of awareness. They committed to the time of entry, the mask, the carpet, the distancing of two metres, left a row and no one shook hands and some rushed out to pray the Sunna¹¹ at home.

Disapproval of the Application of Precautionary Measures

In contrast to the citizens' oversight and concerns, a number of tweeters raised questions about the permissibility of wearing a mask for men, another about the permissibility of praying at home instead of congregating in the mosque and a third tweeter requested a fatwa from a sheikh about applying the distance between worshippers:

Is prayer with a mask permissible for men?

¹¹ "A Sunnah prayer (Arabic: صلاة السنة) is an optional or supererogatory salah (ritual prayer) that can be performed in addition to the five daily salah, which are compulsory for all Muslims." (Google)

If my children and I pray at home until the danger has gone completely, is there a sin in that?

Do we take this as a fatwa? May God bless you, Sheikh.

Other tweets took this disapproval to a further level by comparing applying social distancing in mosques and not adhering to it in public places and linking this to a loss of reverence and tranquillity in prayer:

People are close to each other in parks and on beach, in restaurants and rest houses; they have returned. In the rows of prayer, fear God Almighty, we have lost reverence and tranquillity.

They returned to the rows of prayer in mosques; people were close together in parks, amusement parks, markets and restaurants. And separated in prayer, fear God, we lost reverence in prayer and peace...

Figure 4

Referring to the Fatwa to Preserve the Safety of the Citizen

In contrast to the previous disapproval and the use of a fatwa to check on the permissibility of applying precautionary measures, the fatwa was used for the exact opposite: as evidence of the permissibility of these practices. The first was from a position of reluctance to accept it, while the other was out of certainty and a desire to extend it to a larger segment of society:

I hope you will reassure those with chronic diseases that prayer at home is permissible until the end of the epidemic.

#Veryimportant and #urgent, we ask the Council of Senior Scholars @ssa_at or @Saudi_Moia to address a word or fatwa to those who attend the mosque to the worshippers without a mask, in clear disregard and complacency with the instructions of the #MinistryofHealth @SaudiMOH, and this irresponsible behaviour may cause the transmission of infection to their fellow worshippers, especially since the mosque is considered a gathering place.

Among the tweets, some discussions emerged between the disobedient tweeters and those who supported the application of precautionary measures and disparagement of the application of distance between worshippers and wearing a face mask. For example, one of the tweeters commented, *A distance of two metres is too much*, and the response to him was that it was applied in the Great Mosque of Mecca in addition to the distance set by the World Health Organization. The deliberation and discussion among the tweeters on the subject of the face mask were as follows:

How do you want the imam to recite with the face mask?

We read normally.

If the imam takes off the face mask and does not instruct the worshippers, then the worshippers are negligent about protection, and this is what I saw in the mosque. If it's regarding the reciting, the imam could lower his face mask

while reciting, and following the kneeling, he can lift it up again. Leniency in such practices could take us to the edge. Allah is sufficient for us! Most excellent is He in Whom we trust!”

Finally, what is striking in the interaction in the tweets by the Ministry of Islamic Affairs is a proposal: the Saudisation of imams; here, Saudisation appears as a facet of national identity. Was the claim due to the pandemic and the statistics that showed the high rates of non-Saudi infected with the Covid-19 pandemic? Or was this due to observations that non-Saudi imams did not adhere to precautionary measures? These are questions outside the scope of this work and their answers raise a different topic beyond this paper’s scope.

Conclusion and Discussion

This paper posed two questions: How did the Covid-19 pandemic reinforce Saudi national identity? And, at the same time, how did it challenge the religious identity facets? I tried to answer these questions by employing a qualitative approach in collecting and analysing a group of tweets on two twitter accounts: The Saudi Ministry of Health and the Ministry of Islamic Affairs, between March–July 2020. Thematic analysis approach was adopted.

The most prominent results were summarised in that the Saudi Ministry of Health and Islamic Affairs employed the national and religious identity by reinforcing the former and facing the challenges of the latter, using a discourse that focuses on social responsibility, heroism, duty and the concept of national health security—all with the aim of raising the level of commitment to precautionary measures during the pandemic of Covid-19. The challenge of religious identity appeared in avoiding handshakes, denouncing the distance between worshippers and wearing a face mask.

Looking at the literature review, we believe that this work will enrich studies that have discussed Covid-19, specifically within the fields of human and social sciences. It slightly overlaps with a limited number of works reviewed earlier, such as the emergence of the symbolism of the championship and the media message presented by the Saudi Ministry of Health compared to the Iraqi Ministry of Health (Al-Anzi, Nahla, 2020). In addition, the

qualitative method has expanded on a number of studies that followed a quantitative approach in collecting and analysing data on the Twitter platform, which provides in-depth social aspects of the pandemic.

This work's contribution is a step forward for what future studies can address in the fields of humanities and social sciences in relation to the Covid-19 pandemic: for example, "domesticating" precautionary measures such as the face masks and social distancing, the sustainability of adhering to them after the pandemic ends, turning the face mask into a cosmetic luxury and how different segments of society, like commercial organisations, reacted to the precautionary measures. Most importantly, how did identity fit into various aspects, such as religion, nationality, gender, family, etc., within this crisis?

Finally, this paper falls within the field of interdisciplinary studies, combining the two tracks of sociology and digital media, given that values are part of identity and that the media discourse was reflective and problematic in the transformations of the individual and society during the crisis of the Covid-19 pandemic.

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